

D7.5 Action-Plan for Community of Practice

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CDUE	Communication, dissemination, upscaling and exploitation
CoP	(online) Community of Practice
D	Deliverable
M	Month
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This D7.5 Action-Plan for establishing a Community of Practice (CoP) is written in the frame of WP7 – Information, Communication, Upscaling and Capacity-Building, Task 7.2 Europe-LAND’s project branding, communication material and digital outreach of target groups of the Europe-LAND project under Grant Agreement No. 101081307.

It outlines a plan on how to utilize social media to build and maintain a virtual Community of Practice, consisting of land-use and land-cover stakeholders, from academia, policy, practice, industry and governance to maximize the outreach of the project, i.e. Europe-LAND’s target groups, and creating an interactive platform for thematic cooperation and discussion across the EU.

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1. Introduction

The aim of the Community of Practice (CoP) around the Europe-LAND project is to create, manage and monitor a long-lasting thematic, knowledgeable and cooperative platform on current and future European land use and land management issues for stakeholders and project partners to inform, learn from and about each other’s knowledge needs and activities. The Community of Practice will act as a bridge between different stakeholder groups and networks as well as the project to identify and share relevant knowledge. This Action Plan is inspired by the European Commission JRC’s “The Communities of Practice Playbook” in its approach to define, build and maintain a community (European Union, 2021).

Figure 1 shows the schematic structure of the CoP. The main areas of the work conducted within the CoP are community management, the engagement of the community members and active knowledge sharing both with and between the members. This Action Plan lays out the proposed work to build and maintain the CoP to achieve the set aim of the community.

Figure 1: The Community of Practice (CoP), adapted from “The Communities of Practice Playbook”, (European Union, 2021).

For Europe-LAND, this also supports the underlying strategic approach which aims at supporting the visibility, uptake and, consequently, an accelerated exploitation of project results. Within this platform, Europe-LAND partners disseminate, communicate and explain project outcomes to key stakeholders, such as government agencies, cities, industry, academia and practice partners. The CoP supports the overall impact of the project, as defined in the Grant Agreement (see Table 1), by addressing key target

stakeholder groups and delivering project information to them and engaging them in scientific discourse on the platform.

Table 1: Key Elements of Impact supported by the CoP.

Target groups	Outcomes	Impacts
<p>All stakeholders involved in land management: farm federations and agriculture organisations, spatial planning engineers, NGOs and citizen associations.</p> <p>Scientific community: researchers, particularly those involved in land use and land cover changes, spatial modelling tools, biodiversity challenges, and climate change mitigation and adaptation.</p> <p>Decision-makers and technicians: policy makers, local authorities, regulatory agencies.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanded knowledge in sustainable land use strategies; • Promotion of stakeholder engagement and support to EU plans and policies; • Guidance for targeted sustainable land-use strategies and policies on EU, national and regional levels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific: The project’s scientific findings and training materials are widely used across the EU and beyond to enable a change of mindset and improved, evidence-based policy-making; • Societal: Increased stakeholder awareness on climate change and biodiversity challenges leading to application of land-use strategies in European countries; • Economic: Integrated tools are developed for improving land-use management across Europe and supporting investment and policy-making decisions.

This Action Plan describes in detail the means by which the Europe-LAND project team plans to achieve this aim and meet related key performance indicators.

2. Means of the Community of Practice

The Europe-LAND CoP will be using LinkedIn as an effective mass communication tool widely used within the scientific community and policy makers at national and EU levels, as identified in the scope of the deliverable D9.1 CDUE-Plan submitted in M3. The results of the audience analysis are again detailed in Table 2 (see also Table 1, D7.1 CDUE-Plan).

Table 2: Target audience groups and preferred communication channels, as identified within D7.1.

Target Audience Group	Target audience sub-groups	Preferred communication channels
Land-use stakeholders	e.g. land-users, land-owners, farmers, agriculture organizations, foresters, forestry organizations, landscape and national park authorities	Agricultural Fairs and exhibitions, podcast programs, Social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter (X), website, workshops and webinars, local newspapers, email newsletters
Public authorities	e.g. local, regional and national authorities, regulatory agencies, policy makers, farm federations, citizen associations	Policy briefs and reports, workshops and webinars, stakeholder meetings, media outreach, Social media platforms such as LinkedIn and Twitter (X)
Scientific community	e.g. experts, researchers, NGOs, spatial planning engineers, science communicators	Academic publications, webinars, social media, email newsletters, scientific conferences and events, social media platforms such as LinkedIn and Twitter (X)
Extended target group	General public, consumers, media	Social media platforms such as Twitter (X) and LinkedIn , traditional media, newspapers, podcasts

The previously established Europe-LAND LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/98043467>) will be used to grow and maintain the virtual CoP by attracting distinctive followers. At this point, the use of a dedicated LinkedIn group for the CoP is not planned, as it restricts members' ability to share and re-post contents from the group, potentially limiting the overall reach of updates and project outputs. Rather, content will be directly shared on the page to allow for more open interaction and a wider reach, and the responsible partner has set up a dedicated social media team that gathers and edits relevant news from the partners as well as from external sources to create tailored posts.

It was previously intended in the Grant Agreement and in D7.1 CDUE-Plan to utilize X (formerly Twitter) in addition to LinkedIn to establish the CoP. As the general use of X as an effective mass communication tool was postponed due to some concerns about the platform's future development in M3 of the project (see D7.1 CDUE-Plan, chapter 3.3.2 Online Communication), CoP-related actions will currently not utilize X, but focus on LinkedIn for the time being, as it is recognized for its effectiveness in fostering professional connections and visibility. The utilization of further interactive platforms, e.g. the SDSN network or the EU Mission Adaptation Community, will be assessed continuously and actively pursued. In addition, the project team will reach out to the intended audience and create the envisaged impact also by tapping into the Europe-LAND Stakeholder Pool, established within the D7.6 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (M6) to establish contact with stakeholders and individuals who have given their expressed consent to receive information from the project to promote and further facilitate the CoP on LinkedIn.

3. Content to be created

The content to be created and posted on the Europe-LAND LinkedIn page aims at informing audiences about the project and related topics, highlighting developments in European land-use and land cover science and policy and engage audiences and stakeholders by invoking further discussion. Besides posts on project events, results and publications by project partners, the page will also generate content on new EU policy (e.g. the agreement on the Nature Restoration Law <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7133760720105558017>), and may explore other examples like the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, Common Agricultural Policy reforms, and initiatives under the European Green Deal related to land use, agriculture, biodiversity and climate change. Additionally, the page will share publications from relevant stakeholders (e.g. the IPCC 2023 Synthesis Report <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7102597164605849601>) on related topics aligned with the project's focus. A "Meet Europe-LAND Partners" series is planned, showcasing each project partner with a dedicated post to highlight their scientific and expert contributions to the project and giving space for individual Europe-LAND researchers to share their motivation to work on land-use issues. Furthermore, opinion pieces on related topics are planned (e.g. on plant-based nutrition and its connection to land-use issues <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7100401442858913793>). This might be extended to invite project external stakeholders from practice and academia, including the sister projects, to share their views on highly discussed topics.

Concerning timing, posts are strategically scheduled around project events, holidays, releases or publications from partners, the EU or other relevant organizations, global and national action days (such as World Environment Day, International Green Week, etc.). The schedule is planned beforehand, and posts are tracked in a list, detailing the month, title, responsible person for posting, scheduled release date and actual release date. The aim is to publish consistently every week to keep the audiences engaged with new content while also ensuring that individual posts do not overshadow one another.

Whenever possible, the content will also be linked to other outreach activities of the Europe-LAND project, for example the podcast series and the official project website. Furthermore, project partners will use their expert networks and websites to promote the CoP.

Figure 2: The Europe-LAND LinkedIn page.

4. Engagement with Audience

In addition to using LinkedIn to post content to inform followers about project outputs, other strategies will be employed to actively engage with stakeholders on the platform.

- From time to time, posts will use polls on highly discussed issues or pose open questions to the comments to engage followers and receive direct feedback and input from them.
- Relevant stakeholders, partners and organisations will be tagged wherever possible, to maximize the reach of posts.
- Hashtags frequently used on similar and relevant content will be used to extend the reach and ensure that the posts will be more visible to users searching for land-use related topics. As a

base for all posts, the hashtags #Landuse; #Sustainability; #Agriculture and #CINEA were identified within the D7.1 CDUE-Plan submitted in M3, with the list to be enlarged depending on the topic addressed, e.g. #biodiversity or country hashtags when e.g. Europe-LAND's partners or case studies are featured.

LinkedIn will also be used to actively follow and connect with stakeholders and relevant EU projects by sharing and commenting on relevant posts as well as sending invitations to project events.

5. Moderation of responses, comments and interactions

The Community of Practice is meant to be open to all audiences on LinkedIn and invites followers and other users to engage with the posts directly via polls or the comments. For fruitful and inclusive discussions, it is important to also accept critical, negative or controversial comments, however hurtful or harmful comments need to be monitored and restricted, in order to protect individuals and the community as a whole. The HAW team as WP 7 leader is therefore responsible and will monitor the public comment sections on the posts made to the project page. Fake news, harmful or discriminatory comments will be deleted.

6. Monitoring and Evaluation

As the Community of Practice plays an important role in the impact generation of the project, the effectiveness of the planned strategy will be monitored and evaluated as part of the M&E Framework (D1.8). Within the Grant Agreement and reiterated in the CDUE-Plan (D7.1), there are defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of the communication and dissemination strategy. Some of those also relate to the CoP, as listed below in Table 3.

Table 3: Key Performance Indicators for the impact related to the CoP.

Key performance indicator	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Number of followers on social media	<500	500-1000	>1000
Number of interactions (e.g. likes, comments, shares)	<800	800-1200	>1200
Members in community of practice	<1000	1000-1500	>1500

The WP 7 lead at HAW is responsible for monitoring the work undertaken and providing the relevant information for evaluation within the M&E framework (T1.4) periodically.

7. Conclusion

The Action Plan for the Community of Practice provides a strategic framework for the communication effort to be undertaken throughout the project duration on the project's LinkedIn page, to create a platform for stakeholders and project partners to exchange knowledge on project relevant topics, enter into a dialogue with each other, to convey and elaborate key messages and results of the project.

It lays out the means with which the CoP will be built and maintained, the type of content to be created, how the project team will facilitate and interact with CoP members, how interactions will be managed and, lastly, how the CoP will be continuously monitored and evaluated.

As such, the CoP serves to disseminate, communicate and support the upscaling and exploitation of its knowledge and results by reaching out to a wide range of international stakeholders in an innovative manner.

References

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